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Reading Climate Change in Indira Goswami's *The Moth Eaten Howdah of the Tusker*

Dr. Chandrima Sen
Assistant Professor,
Department of English,
Bodoland University.

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Abstract:

Indira Goswami's *The Moth Eaten Howdah of the Tusker* was primarily analysed as a socio-political novel. The present paper argues the novel's most exclusive offering to the domain of climate change is more explicit in tone and essence. The story indeed deploys socio-political issues but it also accomplishes a course of allegories by focussing on different forms of climate change in relation to social inequality. The different allegories here revolve around the interaction between the protagonist, Indranath and those he encounters in his life. The different characters' interaction also functions as allegories of the entire North-eastern region, local and global landscape. The novel's climate change allegories indeed raise socio-political concerns, these are often raised as contested issues. The paper also discusses the allegorical phenomenon through the novel's narrative framework, particularly its intent narrative. It also provides a means for Goswami to allegorically explore the means in which the local enthusiasts experience change in climate that again affects their culture.

Keywords: climate change, society, individual, self, allegory.

Introduction-

Indira Goswami is one of the most acclaimed writers in the history of Indian writing in English. Goswami received the Sahitya Akademi Award in 1983 and, many more awards

are there to her credit. Her novels talk about individuality, society, climate and a conglomeration between the three. When her career was at its peak, she wrote *The Moth Eaten Howdah of the Tusker* that deals with an indigenous Assamese community. The novel portrays an Assamese Brahmin society, the Sattrra culture in Assam, the status of widowed women, the rural sanctity and the remarkable reformations that take place between 1948 and “Nineteen eighty-one” (Goswami 345).

The novel revolves around the issues of female agency, social categorization and climatic challenges. These aspects are explored through the cast of female characters, namely Durga, Saru Gossainee and Giribala. They also manifest sequential individual growth and regional progression. On top of everything, Goswami retains her male character, Indranath at the centre. Her female characters namely Durga, represents loneliness and seclusion, Saru Gossainee embodies anticipation and hope and, Giribala, exemplifies provocation and defiance. Further, Indranath is at the centre. When Goswami talks about Indranath, she focuses more on his intentions to prohibit opium promotion in and around Amaranga Sattrra. She rightly writes: “... the air was full of the fragrance of new *ahu*¹ paddy. Now it was replaced by the odour of opium” (16). As a schoolboy, Indranath used to feel the pulps of red pumpkins and their seeds and the odour of fried *pan*² leaves. Along with climate change and individual growth, people turn more into abstract reality than into concrete belongingness. Goswami desperately utters terms with the initial ‘d’- “Decay, death, destruction” (Goswami 17) that depicts her association with climate and her assertiveness towards change. The novel is an open-ended one with a lot of references to transformation and challenges.

The structure of the novel encompasses social reality, individual progression and psychological transgression. The novel begins with the protagonist Indranath. The contextual approach centres on a full-moon calm and silent night. The references to women playing *golokdham*³ (1) in their inner chambers, the fragrance of *sewali*⁴ (1) flowers, and the *Jatra*⁵

troupe contextualize the socio-ecological entity prevalent in the village. Indranath was supposed to be the would-be *adhikar*⁶ (2). The coo-coo of the *fesuluka*⁷ (3) bird, the sweet sound of the Jagalia river, and the rustle of the *muga mekhela*⁸ (3) touch his mind. It was like riding a road of peace and serenity. The novel can be read as a climate fiction that deals with climate change. Trexler and Putra in their article refer to Robert Macfarlane who says: “Where are the novels, the plays, the poems, the songs, the libretti, of this massive contemporary anxiety?” (Trexler and Putra 185). The genre of climate change acts more like a phenomenon than a mere theory. It works on ideological assumptions and the setting of responses.

Aims and Objectives-

This study aims to uncover the transitions that take place in and around the coastal area of the South Kamrup district of Assam. It also corresponds to the consequences of increased opium consumption and community participation. This study also employs myriad policies to achieve sustainable and comprehensive climate conditions. It also highlights different implications of climate change that affect individual growth, social upliftment and psychological security. The book “Trauma and the Discourse of Climate Change: Literature, Psychoanalysis and Denial” begins and ends with the question “Don’t you see I’m burning?” marked by the author Lee Zimmerman. The present climate catastrophe discovers the advent of change and threat for the generations to come. It also evaluates human-induced factors that are responsible for climatic disruptions.

Representation of Climate Change in Indira Goswami’s *The Moth Eaten Howdah of the Tusker*

Bill Mc Kibben writes “We’ve changed the planet” and so “climate change is already wrecking thousands of lives daily” (Kibben xii). In one instance, Goswami writes: “In the

dead of the night, emaciated figures, almost skin and bones, appeared suddenly from nowhere and fell at the feet of the card players, begging for money. They, were the opium addicts, once respectable farmers and villagers but now pitiful wretches” (Goswami 2). These farmers had undergone lifestyle changes due to the change that took place in the climate. Indranath holds ‘Jokram’ Bhagawati, who is also known as Bhagawati the leech, used to supply pigeons, ducks and rice to the Base camp during wartime. In this context, Goswami writes: “Now all that is no more. The roof of the house resembles an old camel skin. The walls have caved in. The haystack in the courtyard has almost vanished. It is said that Jokram was ruined after coming into contact with a man from Cooch Behar who traded in opium” (Goswami 5). The phrase ‘foul weather’ (9) elaborates on the winds of change ‘blowing over the Sattra’ (9). Further, Durga sanctifies the warmth of the “woodfire, the dense smoke going up in the still atmosphere from green branches... with the colour of ash” (11). The *sal* forest (19), ‘thick greenery’ (19), *kachindariya*¹⁰ grass and *bankuhun*¹¹ plants (18) contribute to the overall natural aroma of the surroundings. Timothy Morton, one of the finest Ecocritics, emphasizes on our “action” to awaken and save our “ecological co-existence” (Morton 17). The opium eaters whom Goswami calls ‘worn-out addicts’ had ‘lost’ their sense long back. She calls them ‘shywick’, people with ‘boorish laughter’ (24). They appeared to be in a state of “drugged euphoria” (36). The toxicity of the so-called drug-addicted people persuaded the villagers to sit by the ‘fireside’ (12) to regain their hope and strength. The novel reads: “The fragrance of *kagji*¹² lime blossoms permeated the air” (14). The narrative concentrates on the aspects of marriage, marginalization of women, patriarchal society and orthodox Brahmin ideals and values.

The items like *ou-tenga*¹³ (141), *barali*¹⁴ fish (142), big *vilayati alu*¹⁵ (142), *joha*¹⁶ rice (142), the ‘decorated bronze plate’ (142), pigeon curry with papaya (140), the *bhagat*¹⁷ of the sattra (155), the *gamucha*¹⁸ (160), the *bogori*¹⁹ (75) fruits etc. cater to the regional flavour

of the village. The 'freshness of the leaves of the *arum*²⁰ plant' (22), the 'silky soft mud' of Jagalia (22), the white dazzling light of the *kamini*²¹ tree (43), glistening *jangur*²² leaves (42), *godhuli gopala*²³ bush' (43), the 'white flowers of the *kathana*²⁴ tree (166) add to the reality of the village. The Shari festival (23), was where all "the deities of the nearby villages and sattras were brought in palanquins to the bank of Jagalia and worshipped" (Goswami 23). The hegemonic structure of Brahmin society also comes to light during Basanti puja (23). There is also a reference to the *amoti*²⁵ ritual (26) when Mother Earth menstruates. The sixth Chapter refers to the *daul*²⁶ festival. Further, the novel reads: "The soft silken light that covered the trees and shrubs suddenly gave way to darkness" (Goswami 102).

Nature writes Goswami "was draped in green on both the banks of Jagalia" (Goswami 335). All the scenes were so precious to him. They were a part of his childhood innocence and growing experience. The society she talks about was based on a patriarchal framework that resulted from a colonial mindset. A renowned poet, Pradip Kumar Patra writes in the Introduction of the Journal "Transcript: Journal of Literature and Cultural Studies": "...climate crisis converges with contemporary capitalist's quest for perpetual growth" (Patra 6). Goswami also shows how the change in climate intersects with the current bourgeois enterprise. towards the end of the novel, Indranath seems to feast "his eyes in the landscape with its many shades of green" (Goswami 336). These shades are categorized into dark, soft and parrot green. In one instance, he remembers his ancestors being "lured by the sight of such natural beauty" (Goswami 340). Now he says: "How green it was! How beautiful it was on both sides of the road..." (Goswami 340). Lee's reference to the Tyndall Centre for Climate Change Research insists on how we the human beings "continue" (2) with the present perspectives and "acknowledge" that human beings do "have choice". This sort of continuity and acknowledgement pronounces a state of boredom that casts a spell on Indranath's life. The novel ends on an optimistic note. As Chapter Fourteen reads: "We must

be very strict. If necessary, even very cruel" (Goswami 278). However, Goswami writes: "Now only a shadow remains of those glorious traditions of commerce and trade" (Goswami 279).

The opium eaters were from distant places like Garodhuli, Chikarhati, Majhkuchi and other villages. Indranath felt disgusted with them. The novel reads: "They were in a state of drugged euphoria"(36), heading towards a 'dark future' (36). With these opium eaters, neglect and desolation overshadowed the village. For Indranath, disappointment and frustration radiate an enchantment on the entire landscape. "He felt as if he was in a cremation ground" (37). Goswami writes: "The non-cooperation movement of Mahatma Gandhi opened our eyes to the evils of opium eating". (38). Here, she insists on the uprooting and discarding of this hundred and fifty-year-old problem. Indranath adopts the catalytic method to go deep into the matter. He recollects that a committee during the Presidentship of Dinabandhu Andrews has proposed that the trade of opium trade shall "be abolished within the jurisdiction of Assam Council. However, the British Government was reluctant to lose its revenue from opium trade, and had promoted and increased the opium sales considerably" (38). Indranath could read the mind of the white Sahibs that they feed us opium "to break our strength, to make our voice weak" (40). Towards the end: "In every house, there was an opium den and fortunes were sinking" (214). Whereas, in reply, they say: "Oh! Brothers! Sirs! Have pity on us! We took opium only to relieve the pain in our backs, otherwise how could we work the tread-mill for husking rice or plant seedlings in the fields ... We beg you to save us" (215).

From the novel's beginning, such kind of lexical impulses reflect Indranath's experience of the world as propelled by change and evolution. The psychoanalytic accounts of the people seem to indulge with the crisis in the climate. The novel encompasses present facts and possible prophecies. It also appears to be a social manifestation of ideals and values

on the one hand and desires and amusements on the other. Goswami emerges as a significant writer to arouse the issue of climate change in the early 1940s and late 1980s. The setting sets the socio-cultural and socio-political overtone, which is a result of human irresponsibility. The apparent human development that claims towards capitalist production results in the change in climate. Pope Francis declares that climate change provides "... control over an external object" (106). The abrogation of all irregularities is the result of market emergence, economic residues and promising modernity. Leiserowitz elaborates: "As human beings, we are exquisitely attuned to what is happening to our immediate environment" (Interview). It turns out to be what is called climate psychology.

Eileen Crist writes that the dominant discourses of climate change usher for the "industrial-consumer complex" (55) that calls for change and transformation. The values and principles are disrupted in society due to the collapse of traditional and ethical essence and also due to the increasing capitalist formulations. It acts as a challenge and emerges as a prompt diversifier. The rationality of a particular society is agitated by the gradual effect of narcotics and their consumerist intoxication.

Climate change is now a global phenomenon. The increasing emission of greenhouse gases articulates the need to counter the challenge of climatic hazards. Climate change not only accelerates mental orientation but also psychological values. Johns Putra rightly notes: "Climate change is depicted not just as an internal or psychological problem but for its external effects, often as part of an overall collapse including technological, over-reliance, economic instability and increased social division". (Putra 269).

In the Introduction, Young refers to the "patterns of human behaviour that contribute to climate change" (5). He writes: "With support, recognition can lead to informed action" (5). Further, Mossner claims that climate change "is a phenomenon that is too abstract and too vast in its spatial and temporal dimensions to allow for easy visualization" (Mossner 18).

Suzanne Keen refers to the effects of empathy in the novel. The words such as 'education' and 'action' are some of the buzzwords in the discourse of climate change. This novel serves as a stimulus to environmental justice and sustainable development.

This paper attempts to locate the consumerist aspect of the discourse on climate change. The British eco-philosopher, Rupert Read writes that consumerism is "a piece of false consciousness" (Read 51). He is of the view that "it misplaces responsibility from the system onto the individuals, whose alleged 'need' for products drives the system"- as Young writes in his book. Capitalistic sentiment is one of the salient features of the Victorian era. Further, Klein names the real cause of climate change as 'capitalocene'. It is the capital which is to be blamed. Moreover, Greta Thunberg writes about the importance of climate literacy which according to Young will serve as an "emerging ecological civilization" (Young 43).

Conclusion-

Indira Goswami brings forth the aspect of capitalocene to manifest the idea of climate change. Greta manifests the reciprocity of environment and private enterprise. Young cites Arundhati Roy, who, in her "Arthur Miller Freedom to Write Lecture" probes into the affinity between man and nature. Roy writes: "as we lurch into the future ..." (Roy 14) we are "dictated by capitalism" (Roy 56). Goswami portrays her own lived experiences to construct her fictional base that reflects the reality of her times. She mines human qualities, eternity, social evil and corporeality. Her characters and setting acknowledge the aspect of women empowerment and climatic enlightenment. Malashri Lal once, said, "I try to write from the direct experiences of my life. I only mould these experiences with my imagination". Lal also quotes Mamoni who says: "If I were to write an epitaph for myself it would be 'Here lies a humanist'". When she calls herself a humanist, she aims to convey nature's stale presence in

everyone's lives by reconfiguring the climatic conditions. She seems to view capitalism as one of the main hazards of climate change. It disrupts human livelihood in all possible ways. She muses in *The Moth Eaten Howdah of the Tusker*.

The novel reads: "Ever since opium has eaten up this *sattra*, robbery has increased everywhere. Even from our attic, elephant's tusks have been stolen" (Goswami 181). Indranath regards this to be a 'black deed' (Goswami 182). The *sattra* seems to be inhabited by both good and evil minded people with evil intentions. She says: "In every house, there was an opium den and fortunes were sinking" (Goswami 214). She also says: "It is all due to that evil thing, opium! Soon after it entered the *sattra*, sticks have rained blows on the back of us unfortunate women. The days are so bad now!" (Goswami 213). The women opium eaters like Saru Gossainee would say: "Have pity on us! We took opium only to relieve the pain in our backs, otherwise how could we work the tread mill for husking rice or plant seedlings in the fields?" (Goswami 215).

The novel reads that the disease of opium eating had spread by "Muslims and Rajputs" (Goswami 278). On the South Bank of the *Sattra*, seventy per cent of the people are opium addicts. Most of them are merchants. They are wealthy. Their trade extends up to the Pacific, the Indian Ocean and the Arabian Sea. They are now scattered all over and are now reduced to the status of lower caste. Their glorious traditions of trade and commerce have now shifted towards the "Marwari and Bihari businessmen" (Goswami 280-281).

Indranath, a Vaishnavite and a follower of Vaishnavism and Vaishnavite scripture caters to the humanist philosophy and moral values. The lines read: "Everything lies in the hands of human beings! Yes, the hands of men and women!" Indranath seems to preserve and protect his immediate habitat, with education, knowledge and wisdom. When the habitat will be insecure, the climate will also be affected. Goswami here narrates Indranath's quest for the

lost glory and serenity of the region. She also adheres to juxtapose the link between changing weather conditions and man's changing attitudes towards the cosmos.

The name of the novel is apt in the sense that the moth appears to engulf the regional sanctity. She tries to uncover the opium trade in the North-Eastern part of India and the rise of global capitalism. The engagement of several individuals towards the selling of opium seems to be at a larger enterprise. Trocki posits the involvement of the British Empire, trade and capitalism: "Gold and silver from the West crossed the Atlantic or the Pacific, it ultimately found its way to Asia ..." (Trocki 55). She endures the problems of environmental biodiversity, the issue of disbelief, and the capitalistic bent of mind that halts ordinary people and advances the new dynamics of making a corporeal world.

Notes:

*ahu*¹ – a customary expression which indicates fury or anger

*pan*² – betel leaf

*golokdham*³ - a game of dice which is popular among the women in South Kamrup

*sewali*⁴ - a white Indigenous flower that smells sweet and can be used as vegetable, also

*jatra*⁵ – an itinerant group of theatrical performers that are found chiefly in the villages enacting plays from Indian classics

*adhikar*⁶ – administrative head

*fesuluka*⁷ - the fork tailed shrike

*muga mekhela*⁸ – a variety of wild silk, Assamese women's long skirt, tied at the bottom or round the waist

*sal*⁹- a kind of hardwood tree

*kachindariya*¹⁰- a type of tall grass

*bankuhum*¹¹- a plant with purple flowers

*kagji*¹²- sweet-smelling lime

*ou-tenga*¹³- elephant apple

*barali*¹⁴- a kind of river fish without scales

*vilayati alu*¹⁵- an imported potato which the people of Kamrup district consider to be local

*joha*¹⁶- a fine variety of rice

*bhagat*¹⁷- a holy man

*gamucha*¹⁸- a particular cloth to wipe the body

*bogori*¹⁹ – a kind of wild berry tree

*arum*²⁰- a species of flowering plant

*kamini*²¹- a kind of white flower

*jangur*²² – an Indigenous tree

*godhuli gopala*²³- evening, an Indigenous flower that blooms in the evening

*kathana*²⁴- a wild and thick creeper

*amoti*²⁵- biggest religious communion in North-East India

*daul*²⁶- a famous festival of colours

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